

EDITORIAL

Knowledge, research and experience are the cornerstones of our dental profession. In the evidence hierarchy, systemic reviews with or without meta analysis are at the top of the pyramid and provides the best evidence and ranks higher than randomized controlled trials followed by cohort studies and case controlled studies case series/reports. The Cochrane collaboration is an international voluntary organization that prepares, maintains and promotes the accessibility of systemic reviews of the effects of healthcare. Cochrane Database of systemic reviews are examples of filtered resources. Unfiltered resources can be accessed through EMBASE, MEDLINE, PUBMED etc. Narrative reviews lack systemic search and do not qualify as adequate evidence to answer critical questions. The above evidence hierarchy will act as a guide for our contributing authors. It gives me immense pleasure to announce the launch of our educational mouthpiece, “Journal of Orofacial Rehabilitation”, the official publication of Indian Prosthodontic Society West Bengal State Branch. I sincerely thank all office bearers, branch members and authors for contributing to the success of this journal.

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